

A multi-objective optimization of FCL and DOCR settings to mitigate distributed generations impacts on distribution networks

The integration of Distributed Generators (DGs) has brought notable improvements in reliability and power quality for meeting load demands within networks. However, this advancement has also introduced considerable challenges to the protection systems employed. The significant increase in DG penetration alters the network's overall impedance and substantially elevates fault current levels. Consequently, certain network nodes or buses face critical conditions, surpassing the handling capacity of circuit breakers (CB), thereby disrupting existing relay coordination settings.

To counter these challenges, the integration of fault current limiters (FCLs) emerges as a viable solution. These FCLs effectively curtail short circuit currents within the permissible limits of switchgear ratings. However, owing to their substantial cost, it becomes imperative to strategically position and size the FCLs optimally. This optimization should maintain the protection system's effectiveness across diverse network operation states.

In this context, a research initiative has been undertaken to devise a combined protection coordination scheme involving fault current limiters (FCLs) and directional overcurrent relay (DOCR) settings. This scheme is optimized through a multi-objective hybrid optimization technique. The primary objective is to ascertain the minimal FCL size while minimizing investment costs, ensuring adherence to relay coordination constraints at high-fault level buses. This coordination scheme, facilitated by user-defined relay characteristics (UDC), enhances DOCR coordination performance by optimizing conventional inverse relay constants (A&B) alongside parameters like TSM & Ipu. This joint optimization aims to mitigate electromagnetic stresses, prevent costly switchgear replacements, and preempt relay malfunctions.

The efficacy of this proposed technique has been rigorously evaluated by its implementation on both radial (IEEE-33 Bus) and meshed (IEEE 30-Bus) Distribution Networks (DNs). Through the optimized sizing of FCLs and relay settings, the results substantiate the technique's effectiveness in preserving relay coordination performance amidst the presence of DGs and FCLs, whether the grid connection is ON or OFF.

This comprehensive approach not only addresses the challenges posed by increased DG integration but also showcases a systematic methodology to optimize protection systems, ensuring network stability and operational resilience in dynamic grid environments.

DOI; [10.1016/j.ijepes.2022.108827](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijepes.2022.108827)